

Tumor microenvironment has clinical significance in terms of prognosis and therapy prediction

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Abstract- At this point, the tumor microenvironment (TME) clinical significance in terms of prognosis and therapy prediction has become obvious. The TME is comprised of a varied population of cytokine/chemokine-releasing cells, which results in a local immune response. Colorectal cancer cells also produce antigens that are responsible for initiating an antitumor response. A better clinical prognosis is linked to a large number of effector T cells, which are predominantly made up of CD8⁺ CTLs, and a low concentration of regulatory T cells. Concentration of PD-L1 and its mutation load are both predictors of a response to anti-PD-L1 treatment. Despite ICI clinical trials showing that ICIs work, patients' responses to ICIs differ depending on the indication. With the emergence of TME-based biomarkers, we will demand additional TME-based biomarkers for more accurate therapies. The spatial-temporal interaction of immune system cells will also need to be investigated, in addition to current test criteria such as the identification of somatic changes, measurement of TMB, loss of HLA locus, and assessment of PD-L1 expression. Also, in order to accurately identify ICI therapy's most favorable recipients, identifying patients who will most benefit from ICI therapy solely or in combination with other treatment modalities is crucial.

I. INTRODUCTION

The accumulation of driver mutations in the afflicted tissue, the failure of immune surveillance, and the effect of the tumor microenvironment (TME) are all examples of molecular pathways that play a role in the onset and development of cancer. Thousands of cancer genomes have been sequenced since the discovery of the adenoma-to-carcinoma sequence in the early 1990s, and the accumulation of somatic mutations in critical signaling pathways is assumed to be a driving factor for cancer's temporal and spatial biological evolution (1). The "big bang concept," which is based on huge data and states that uniform proliferation of diverse clones occurs until the malignant transformation is complete, has been amended by the concept of selective pressure of driver mutations (2). One of the key consequences is the development of biological medicines that target specific genetic abnormalities in malignancies, such as EGFR amplification in colorectal cancer (CRC) (3). In addition to somatic alterations initiating and maintaining tumor progression, there is growing evidence that the immune system plays multiple roles in cancer prevention, including combating viral infections, preventing proinflammatory environments, and eliminating tumor cells, as well as steps involved in immunosurveillance and immunoeediting. The presence of tumor infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) is critical for cancer patients' prognosis and treatment, and the tumor microenvironment (TME) plays a key role in tumor development and immunotherapy response.

CRC is a genetically and biologically diverse disease that requires molecular characterization. TME is made up of stromal and immune cells, and the tumor mass is made up of transformed epithelial cells that accumulate driving mutations. The classic adenoma-to-carcinoma sequence and the serrated adenoma pathway are two morphological multi-step processes based on morphology. The chromosomal instability (CIN) pathway and the microsatellite instability (MSI) route are two significant molecular pathways that have been discovered via genetic research. The CpG island methylator phenotype (CIMP) is sometimes referred to as a third molecular route, but it overlaps with MSI positive, according to TCGA (5, 6).

The CIN route is the most frequent, accounting for roughly 80% of sporadic CRCs. Large chromosomal rearrangements and frequent somatic copy number alterations are common characteristics (CNV). CIN positive CRCs have known numerous mutations in driver genes associated with the adenoma-to-carcinoma transition, such as APC, TP53, SMAD4, PIK3CA, KRAS, and others (5). APC and MUTYH gene mutations can be passed down and lead to familial adenomatous polyposis coli (FAP) and MUTYH-associated polyposis, respectively. Due to the inactivation of the mismatch repair (MMR) gene, a smaller genetic subgroup of CRCs is characterized by a large number of mutational events, which shows high MSI (MSI-H). Cancer predisposition Lynch syndrome can be identified in people with MSI-positive malignancies (LS). When MMR gene mutations are somatic, sporadic MMR-deficient CRCs frequently have a particular mutation V600E in the BRAF gene, which is practically absent in LS patients, and have a serrated adenoma phenotype. MSI-H CRCs have a high mutation load and a large

infiltration of immune cells, especially cytotoxic CD8⁺ T-lymphocytes (CTLs). They're known as hypermutated cancers, and they frequently react to checkpoint inhibitor treatment (7, 8).

There are still a few ultramutated CRCs lacking MSI that have inactivating germline and/or somatic mutations in the DNA polymerases POLE or POLD genes (9). Due to the significant number of missense and frameshift mutations, these tumors have a significant infiltration of immune cells and are ideal candidates for immunotherapy. More work is being done to subtype CRC more thoroughly based on gene expression. CRCs have been subclassified into four consensus molecular subtypes (CMS) based on the results of six separate research groups (10). CMS1 relates to the MSI-H group, and tumors mostly emerge through the serrated route, have a high frequency of BRAF V600E mutation and hypermethylation of CpG islands, are invaded by TILs, and have a low number of somatic CNVs. The MSS group has been divided by three pathways: canonical CMS2, metabolic CMS3, and CMS4. Canonical CMS2 tumors have a large number of somatic CNVs in oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes, and they grow from a standard adenoma-to-carcinoma sequence. They also have activation of the WNT and MYC signaling pathways. In comparison to CMS2 and CMS4, the CMS3 subtype has less somatic CNVs and has more hypermutated and hypermethylated tumors. KRAS mutations are prevalent in this subtype, and up to 9 out of 10 metabolic pathways are enriched. In addition, CMS3 and CMS4 had 3 and 5% somatic CNVs for the HER2 gene, respectively. The expression of the epithelial–mesenchymal transition (EMT) and inflammatory genes distinguishes the CMS4 subtype. With infiltrating Treg cells, myeloid-derived suppressor cells, and tumor-promoting macrophages, TME is also pro-inflammatory. Although the CMS subclassification is a relatively robust methodology, the methodologies used for everyday analyses are quite complicated. As a result, developing molecular tests for CMS categorization based on less difficult techniques (11) to assist stratify individuals into molecular subtypes for clinical trials would be desired. Furthermore, characterizing TME, particularly the immunological context and molecular profile, is critical for determining the patient's prognosis and developing more precise sub-type specific therapy options.

II. METHODS FOR STUDYING COLORECTAL CANCER'S IMMUNE CONTEXTURE

The tumor microenvironment (TME) is made up of non-cancerous cells that surround cancer cells and include immune cells and tumor-associated stromal cells. Interactions between the tumor and the immune system of the host are part of a tumor's natural history. The tumor genome, which contains genetic changes that result in the presentation of tumor specific antigens (TSAs) or neoantigens on the cell surface and generate an immune response known as tumor immunogenicity (12), determines these interactions. The antigenicity of the TSA or neoantigen, which are identified as non-self by the immune system, determines the immunogenicity of a tumor. TILs and other immune cells are recruited as a result of high immunogenicity (12).

The immunological contexture of CRC is made up of various immune cells of the myeloid or lymphoid lineage, such as macrophages, dendritic cells (DC), natural killer (NK) cells, B- and T-cells. In addition to cell type, the immune contexture includes cell density, functional orientation, and localization in a specific tumor location (13). Serological approaches for assessing cytokine levels or suppression subtractive hybridization for the study of differentially expressed genes in CRC are two simpler ways of evaluating the immune response of tumors (14, 15). There are also a number of high-throughput methods for detecting and quantifying immune cells in solid tumors. These methods differ in their applicability in routine diagnosis and research, as well as their ability to detect immune cells directly or indirectly by evaluating a cell-specific transcriptional signature.

III. METHODS OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EXAMINATION

When a tumour first appears, it triggers a variety of inflammatory and immunological responses. TILs, peritumoral lymphocytes (lichenoid banding), peritumoral lymphoid aggregates with or without germinal centers (Crohn-like reaction), and reactive regional lymph nodes can all be detected by histopathological analysis of H & E stained formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) sections. The first three characteristics are linked to MSI cancers. IHC is more specific in detecting particular subsets of immune cells, such as CD4⁺ on Th cells, CD8⁺ on cytotoxic T-cells, CD45RO⁺ on effector memory T-cells, CD68⁺ on macrophages, and PD-1 on anergic T-cells (16,17,18).

However, because this examination is not part of the standard examination procedures used in everyday practice, it is not commonly employed. Examining the status of MMR deficiency (MSI) or PD-1 rather than particular subtypes of immune cells, which has not been validated for the indication of immunotherapy, is more helpful when contemplating immunotherapy. However, IHC in conjunction with digital pathology has been linked to the calculation of "Immunoscore," a strong prognostic predictor that is still awaiting widespread adoption and validation. Multiplexing immunohistochemical consecutive staining on single slide (MICSSS) or sequential immunoperoxidase labeling and erasing (19, 20) might significantly enhance this approach by examining numerous differentiation markers. Immunofluorescence imaging using confocal microscopy, which can detect up to four fluorophores in one segment (21), has an advantage over IHC. However, this is not appropriate for clinical settings since the handling requires skilled individuals and takes time, which is difficult to fit into everyday practice. Using fluorescent IHC, a multiparameter imaging technique allows for the assessment of up to six parameters (22). The multi-parameter imaging techniques outlined above can be used in research.

Flow cytometry and mass cytometry

Flow cytometry (FC) is a method that sits at the crossroads of regular diagnostics and research. This cell analysis technique uses a flow

cytometer to measure cell characteristics (cell size, cell count, cell cycle, etc.) and protein expression via fluorescently labeled monoclonal antibodies, allowing for highly specific information about individual cells in a rapidly flowing fluid stream as they passed in front of the laser. Cell sorting, also known as fluorescence triggered cell sorting, is another feature of flow cytometers (FACS). This is especially crucial when working with diverse cell populations like those found in cancer tissues. The sample must be treated as a single-cell suspension for effective flow cytometry analysis and examination of each cell separately, which implies that flow cytometry can not provide information on tissue architecture. The phenotyping of CD3⁺ cells in colorectal tumor tissue is demonstrated, as well as the gating of the positive cell population. Gating was established based on cell counts using an isotype negative control antibody. The flow cytometer can measure cells in solution as they pass by the instrument's laser at speeds of 10,000 cells per second or more, and the number of detectable fluorescence parameters can range from one to twenty-seven or more detected at the same time on the same cell. A 17-color panel (23) and later a 27-color panel (24) were effectively employed to explore numerous markers on T cell populations using epitope-specific antibodies coupled to distinct fluorophores on the cell surface. Mass cytometry is a method similar to flow cytometry, except that monoclonal antibodies are labeled with heavy metal isotopes rather than fluorophores in mass cytometry. This adjustment in labeling may decrease spectrum overlap, and the number of factors integrated is bigger overall (25). Isotopes are detected as single cells on a mass spectrometer after cells have been labeled (26).

Currently, this approach is used to examine 40 markers per cell, but it appears that it might be expanded to include 70–100 parameters (27). In human bone marrow samples, mass cytometry revealed the intricacy of immune cell signaling and haematopoietic cell growth, pointing to heterogeneity in drug responses across immune cell subtypes (28). The capacity to assess a wide range of parameters without sacrificing sensitivity is a major benefit of mass cytometry (29). However, there are some cellular characteristics that mass cytometry can not detect, necessitating the use of flow cytometry. Forward and side scatter (FSC and SSC) are two characteristics that allow big granular leukocytes, lymphocytes, doublets of cells, and cellular detritus to be separated (27). Mass cytometry has two major drawbacks: it takes a long time and the experiment might be expensive.

IV. BIOINFORMATICS AND RNA SEQUENCING

The rise of a new scientific area in oncoimmunology, which investigates the immunological environment and uses genomic technologies like as RNA microarrays and RNA sequencing, has been facilitated by the evolution of high-throughput genomic technologies. The investigation of particular gene expression and the discovery of the transcriptional signature of immune genes in the tumor microenvironment is the major emphasis, and it combines complicated laboratory procedures with bioinformatics analysis of transcriptomic data (30). Because the gene expression profiles of purified immune cells were publically accessible, gene expression signatures in surgical samples from individuals with CRC could be analyzed (31). In 105 clinical samples from CRC patients, a comprehensive microarray study of 577 genes implicated in the "immunome" found two clusters of gene expression that were associated with disease-free survival (DFS). In native clinical specimens, gene expression signatures for 28 subclasses of immune cells were identified, and a visualized network of interconnected functions revealed that patients with longer survival expressed genes associated with T cytotoxic surface molecules, cytotoxic T cell-mediated immune response, IL12 and STAT signaling Th1 development, or chemokine receptors development. This groundbreaking discovery sparked further efforts to analyze immune cell gene expression patterns from a variety of clinical samples, leading to the development of many bioinformatics approaches for analyzing transcriptomic data gathered from RNA microarray and RNA sequencing. Cell-type Identification by Estimating Relative Subsets of RNA Transcripts (CIBERSORT) is one approach that uses RNA mixtures from practically any tissue to evaluate cell heterogeneity. As input data, the reference gene expression signature and a few data sets are employed, with the output data represented as a heat map table with stacked bar plot representations of each cell type included in the mixture (33, 34).

A positive prognosis is indicated by the presence of lymphocytes (T-lymphocytes and B-lymphocytes) and particular plasma-cell signatures (34). The interference of the host-immune response at the gene and protein level and tumor growth in CRC were studied by Bindea et al. (28) and Mlecnik et al. (35). They studied tumor-immune infiltrates and genetic variation, both of which potentially influence immune responses. The authors compared the transcription profiles of the most prevalent immune cell subpopulations using immunome, a collection of genes and proteins specific to the immune system. They discovered that the densities of T follicular helper (Tfh) cells and innate cells are higher in early-stage cancers and have a significant influence on survival, but that the density of most T cells decreases as the tumor progresses. B lymphocytes, which have a longer overall life time and can acquire memory phenotypes, were shown to be more prevalent in late-stage tumors. These cells have been found to have a significant role in the development of CRC. The authors also discovered a strong relationship between CXCL13, IL-21, Th1, and Tfh cells, indicating that genes play an important role in immunological contexture (32).

The MCP-COUNTER method is used for robust absolute quantification of transcriptomic data for eight types of immune cells (CD3⁺ T cells, CD8⁺ T cells, cytotoxic lymphocytes, NK cells, B lymphocytes, monocyte-derived cells, myeloid dendritic cells, neutrophils) and two stromal cell sub populations (endothelial cells and fibroblasts) in heterogeneous environments. CMS4 mesenchymal tumors are linked with a proinflammatory, proangiogenic, and immunosuppressive microenvironment, which is linked with poor prognosis, according to research using MCP-counter for the prediction of immune infiltration in CRC. MSI-like CMS1 subtypes were also shown to have larger densities of CD8⁺ and CD68⁺ cells than conventional CMS2 and metabolic CMS3 subtypes with intermediate prognosis, which had minimal immune and inflammatory markers. The presence of cytotoxic T cells and low expression of fibroblast-related genes, which is linked to the existence of cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), is linked to a favourable prognosis and hence the best result for patients. (36.)

The significance of immune contexture in the prognosis of colorectal cancer patients

The CRC tumor mass is made up of a variety of cell types, including tumor cells, immune system cells, and stromal components that influence tumor behavior and patient prognosis. Various approaches can be employed to evaluate tumor infiltration by immune cells, as previously indicated (9, 37). FACS was used to generate key data on the clinical importance of immune cell infiltration in CRC, which was then confirmed by IHC. It has been demonstrated that a large number of effector memory CD45RO+ T cells correlates with the lack of symptoms of early metastatic invasion (38).

Furthermore, it was shown that the presence of large numbers of CD3+, CD8+, and CD45RO+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) in the tumor core (CT) and invasive margin (IM) might indicate a better clinical result (16). In colorectal cancer patients, a high density of immune infiltration represented by CD8+ cells, tertiary lymphoid structures, Treg CD4 + FOXP3 + cells, or CD68+ macrophages exhibited a good predictive relation with overall survival; M2 macrophages revealed the sole unfavorable relation (33). It has also been established that the simultaneous production of effector cytokines such as TNF-, IFN-, and IL2 is related to improved clinical outcomes, and intratumoral TNF-levels are a favorable predictive indicator for overall survival (39). Few studies have looked at the involvement of Regulatory T (Treg) cells in CRC recently. Flow cytometry was utilized in one investigation to find lower levels of circulating Tregs (CD4+, FOXP3+, CD25+, CD127+) in metastatic CRC patients treated with VEGF receptor blockers. Flow cytometry was used to quantify tregs in the peripheral blood of bevacizumab-treated metastatic CRC patients. They discovered that bevacizumab prevented Treg accumulation in metastatic CRC patients' peripheral blood, that anti-VEGF-A medication reduced Treg proliferation in these patients, and that the number of Tregs in metastatic CRC patients was greater than in healthy individuals (40).

The makeup of the immune infiltration varies with tumor stage, and most T cell concentrations are inversely related to tumor stage. Patients with deep infiltration of tumor with memory Th1 cells and high levels of CD8+ cells producing IFN- and granzyme at the time of diagnosis had the best prognosis (32). It has been recommended that "Immunoscore," a system for identifying CD3+ and CD8+ T-cells, be implemented (44). Mlecnik et al. (45) found that identification of tumor infiltration based on IHC for the identification of CD3+ and CD8+ cells can predict disease recurrence and survival better than microsatellite instability testing in a large research including over 4000 CRC patients. IHC can identify the highest immune response against the tumor, which is produced by cytotoxic CD8+ T-lymphocytes (CTLs). Because IHC is the most appropriate tool for regular clinical histopathology diagnosis, the main stream efforts are focused on translating knowledge gained from complicated fluorescent imaging and/or genetic techniques into clinical practice using IHC. An international validation study of the immunoscore based on immunohistochemistry and digital pathology determining the densities of CD3+ and cytotoxic CD8+ T cells on tissue samples from 2681 patients found high reproducibility of the results when compared between different centers and confirmed the prognostic value when compared to the TNM classification (46).

Understanding the interplay between cancer growth and the host immune system of each patient is now the most critical undertaking. Each tumor's carcinogenic process is distinct; yet, cancers with comparable features have comparable pathogenic mechanisms and development patterns (47). Cancer cells interact with their TME during carcinogenesis and typically benefit from local factors, which may assist them to evade the local immune system (33).

T lymphocytes and macrophages, which are found in the tumor center and also in the invasive margin (48), as well as natural killer cells, mast cells, neutrophils, and myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs), which are predominantly found in the invasive margins, make up the TME. High levels of MSI, which are seen in around 15% of CRCs, are linked to lymphocyte infiltration, particularly CD8+ T-cells. MMR insufficiency results in a high number of nonsynonymous and frameshift mutations, which yield a variety of immunogenic peptides, which induce antitumor immune responses (49, 50). MMR-deficient CRCs are therefore immunotherapy prospects. The number of T-cells, particularly CD8+, decreases as the main tumor grows (32). Metastases similarly had lower CD8+ densities than their primary lesions, suggesting that immune cell infiltration is comparable in both the main tumor and the metastases. This raises the prospect that immunotherapies or immune-checkpoint inhibitors may be effective against metastatic cancers.

Colorectal cancer immunotherapy

Tumor immunotherapy is regarded as the fifth pillar of cancer treatment because it takes advantage of immune cell infiltration in the tumor, which causes a powerful anti-tumor immune response. Immunological check point inhibitors are monoclonal antibodies used in treatment to disrupt the interaction between inhibitory immune receptors present on the surface of immune cells and their ligands (ICIs). Programmed cell death-1 (PD-1) is the most prevalent immunological checkpoint, followed by CTLA-4/B7-1/B7-2. PD-L1 expression on malignant cells has been found as a biomarker of responsiveness to anti-PD-(L) 1 therapy (51), and the ICIs have altered oncology practice in various disease locations. T-cells are normally kept inactive by checkpoint inhibitors, which prevent cells from self-damaging. If cancer cells maintain the same inhibitors on their surface and are able to switch T-cells off, the issue occurs. The use of ICIs to break the link between check stations is one possible option. Treatment with ICIs appears to be a promising approach, especially for patients with resistant and late-stage tumors. For example, patients with metastatic melanoma who are treated with Ipilimumab (an anti-CTLA-4 antibody) have a 10-year survival rate. IHC evidence of PD-L1 expression for specific tumor types is currently the sole companion test for anti-PD1 treatment prediction, while the outcomes of several clinical studies have reported inconsistent outcomes for this biomarker. However, it has been demonstrated that tumors

with a high mutation load (TMB) may respond better to ICI. MMR-deficient MSI cancers are the most common kind of colorectal tumor (52). The association between the density and location of CD8+ T cells and the response to PD-L1 blockage was revealed in the case of properly functioning ICIs, and "Immunoscore" was recommended as a prediction metric for therapy (48). TME, as previously stated, comprises antigen-specific CD8+ tumor infiltrating T-cell lymphocytes as well as a range of other immune cells (myeloid-derived suppressor cells, regulatory T cells, tumor-associated macrophages, helper and effector cytotoxic T cells, etc.). Hot tumors are those that have been invaded by a large number of these immune cells and include a high number of T cells, making them more susceptible to immunotherapy (53, 54).

The most ideal pattern for anti-PD (L) 1 treatment is in this sort of tumor, and the main objective is to avoid "hot" tumors from becoming "cool." T-cell infiltration has only been reported on the tumor's periphery, and "cold" tumors are mainly inconspicuous to the immune system, with essentially no tumor antigens and T cells in the TME (55). The technique to deal with types of malignancies that are "cool" tumors with low tumor mutation burden (TMB) and hence not sensitive to ICIs is a difficulty for successful immunotherapy. TMB has been proposed as a biomarker of ICI response based on this discovery (56,57,58). There is a theory that the higher the number of somatic mutations in cancer genomes, the greater the likelihood of a response to ICIs (52). TMB is defined as the frequency of somatic mutations in the tumor genome (as determined by DNA/RNA sequencing). As noted in the MMR deficient CRC with MSI, tumors with a high TMB include more neoantigens on the tumor surface that are identified by T-cells and are more likely to react to ICIs (anti-PD-L1 treatment). In this kind of malignancy, frameshift mutations can promote the development of neoantigens in tumors, which can lead to a larger presence of tumor-reactive T-cells in the TME (59, 60).

Tumors with a low TMB, on the other hand, have a low chance of responding to immunotherapy using ICIs. Knowing TMB can help us distinguish between malignancies with a high or low likelihood of responding to ICIs, but it can not tell us which patients will react to these medications and which will not. Outside of clinical studies, ICI medication must be suggested. Ipilimumab is the only FDA-approved CTLA-4 inhibitor, but there are six other ICIs approved for immunotherapy, including the PD-1 inhibitors nivolumab, pembrolizumab, and cemiplimab, as well as the PD-L1 inhibitors atezolizumab, avelumab, and durvalumab, three of which are also indicated for CRC based on MSI status responsible for high T. The main disadvantage of immunotherapies is that they are not effective in all patients. However, recent clinical studies have shown that intratumoral therapies (in situ vaccination, localized radiation) alone or in combination with systematic immunotherapy can convert COLD tumors into HOT tumors and increase the likelihood of immune checkpoint blockade response (48, 53).

The TME's clinical value in terms of prognosis and treatment prediction is now undeniable. TME comprises a diverse population of cytokine/chemokine-releasing cells that create a local immunological response. Colorectal cancer cells also generate antigens that trigger an anti-tumor response. A better clinical prognosis is related to high numbers of effector T cells, primarily CD8+ CTLs, and low levels of regulatory T cells. High PD-L1 expression and mutation load are both predictors of anti-PD-(L) 1 therapy response. Despite the positive outcomes of ICI clinical studies, the response to ICIs varies depending on the indication. As a result, new TME-based biomarkers will be required for more accurate treatments. The spatial-temporal interaction of immune system cells will need to be evaluated in addition to current test criteria such as detection of somatic alterations, measurement of TMB, loss of HLA locus, and determination of PD-L1 expression. Furthermore, identifying patients who are most likely to benefit from ICI therapy alone or in conjunction with other treatment modalities will be critical. Tumor immunotherapy is regarded as the fifth pillar of cancer treatment because it takes advantage of immune cell infiltration in the tumor, which causes a powerful anti-tumor immune response.

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V. CONCLUSION

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